

Structural Studies on Fe(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), VO(II) and UO₂(II) Complexes of Some 4-oximino-2-pyrazolin-5-ones

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Complexes of Fe(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), VO(II) and UO₂(II) with 4-oximino-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one, 4-oximino-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one, 4-oximino-3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 4-oximino-1,3-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one have been prepared and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity, thermogravimetric analysis, infrared and electronic spectral measurements in conjunction with magnetic susceptibility measurements. All complexes except UO₂(II) complexes are octahedral. UO₂(II) complexes may have higher coordination number.

IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on the effect of ligand field splitting on thermodynamic properties of chelate compounds of some 4-oximino-2-pyrazolin-5-ones we report the preparation and study of Fe(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), VO(II) and UO₂(II) complexes of 4-oximino-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OMPP), 4-oximino-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OMP), 4-oximino-3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OPP) and 4-oximino-1,3-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (ODPP).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of the best quality. The chelating agents were prepared as described earlier¹. In the preparation of metal complexes of Mn(II), Zn(II) and UO₂(II) metal nitrates were used. VOSO₄·H₂O and FeSO₄(NH₄)₂SO₄·6H₂O were used in the preparation of VO(II) and Fe(II) complexes respectively.

In the preparation of all the metal complexes, the following general procedure was used. Metal salt was dissolved in hot distilled water. Hot ethanolic ligand solution in slight excess over the metal: ligand ratio of 1:2 was added to it dropwise and with constant stirring. The complex was formed immediately after addition of 2 g of sodium acetate. The product was filtered and washed well with hot water and then with hot ethanol. The complex was then dried in air. The yield of the complexes was almost quantitative.

Elemental analysis and thermal analysis data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1; magnetic moments at r.t. (30°) and ir (nujol) spectral data in Table 2 and diffuse reflectance spectral data in Table 3. Conductivities of the complexes in DMF were also studied.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) suggest 1:2 (metal: ligand) stoichiometry for all the complexes.

The thermograms were analysed to obtain information about percentage weight loss of water, elimination temperature of water and decomposition temperature of the complexes (Table 1). Lower values of molar conductivities ($\Delta_m = 5 - 40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$) of the complexes in DMF indicate their non-electrolyte nature.

Important infrared band positions of ligands and their metal complexes are listed in Table 2. A medium and broad band observed in 4-oximino-2-pyrazolin-5-ones around 3200 cm⁻¹, which is probably assigned as ν_{OH} of the oximino group. The absence of ν_{OH} in all the metal complexes suggest the removal of proton from the oximino group. The free ν_{OH} is generally found between 3650-3500 cm⁻¹^{2,3} similar to that of alcoholic ν_{OH} . The ν_{OH} of several oximes involving intramolecular or intermolecular hydrogen bonding is remarkably lower and is dependent on the strength of hydrogen bond formed in the oxime molecule⁴. The observed low values of ν_{OH} indicate the presence of intermolecular or intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the ligands. The ligand spectra show a strong band in the region 1682-1707 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ^{5,6}. A similar band is observed in all the metal complexes in the region 1600-1660 cm⁻¹ which may be due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in all metal complexes observed is mainly due to coordinate bond formation^{7,8}.

Two bands of nearly equal intensity observed in the region 1590-1665 cm⁻¹ might be due to cyclic and oximino $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. The first band 1590 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (oxime) while the higher energy band may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cyclic)^{6,9}. In the present study it is observed that $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (oxime) is considerably lowered in all the complexes as compared to the parent ligands. The lowering in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (oxime) is observed mainly due to coordinate bond formation through the nitrogen of the oximino group.

A strong and sharp band in the ligand spectra, in the region 1030-1055 cm⁻¹, may be assigned to

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND TGA DATA

Compound	Found (Calculated) Percentage			Water	Elimination temperature of water °C	Decomposition temperature of compound °C
	Metal	Carbon	Hydrogen			
Fe(OMPP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	11.24 (11.25)	49.04 (48.41)	4.54 (4.06)	17.34 (16.94)	7.00 (7.25)	200
Fe(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	16.34 (16.23)	26.06 (27.90)	3.61 (3.49)	23.29 (24.41)	11.00 (10.47)	230
Fe(OPP) ₂	13.26 (12.92)	48.91 (49.98)	3.51 (3.24)	18.98 (19.43)	nil	230
Fe(ODPP) ₂	9.50 (9.66)	53.45 (52.24)	3.16 (3.80)	14.34 (14.52)	nil	240
Mn(OMPP) ₂	11.91 (11.96)	51.86 (52.30)	3.17 (3.51)	18.85 (18.30)	nil	320
Mn(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O)	17.22 (16.89)	29.03 (29.55)	3.84 (3.32)	25.41 (25.85)	5.50 (5.54)	330
Mn(OPP) ₂	12.82 (12.74)	50.15 (50.13)	3.77 (2.80)	19.00 (19.48)	nil	350
Mn(ODPP) ₂	9.78 (9.41)	60.64 (61.75)	2.88 (3.46)	14.22 (14.40)	nil	325
Zn(OMPP) ₂	14.44 (13.92)	52.19 (51.13)	3.74 (3.43)	18.14 (17.89)	nil	350
Zn(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	18.17 (18.49)	27.49 (27.18)	3.53 (3.42)	24.63 (23.77)	10.20 (10.18)	—
Zn(OPP) ₂ H ₂ O	14.20 (14.22)	47.80 (47.03)	4.13 (3.07)	18.85 (18.28)	4.00 (3.92)	350
Zn(ODPP) ₂	11.35 (11.00)	59.71 (60.67)	4.39 (3.39)	14.02 (14.15)	nil	360
[VO(OMPP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ H ₂ O	9.28 (10.04)	46.75 (47.35)	2.82 (3.97)	17.75 (16.56)	7.00 (7.10)	235
[VO(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ₂ H ₂ O	15.02 (14.34)	26.56 (27.05)	3.76 (3.40)	22.95 (23.66)	10.00 (10.14)	220
VO(OPP) ₂	10.83 (11.49)	48.00 (48.77)	2.64 (2.73)	18.36 (18.96)	nil	290
VO(ODPP) ₂	8.62 (8.55)	59.67 (60.51)	3.02 (3.39)	15.00 (14.11)	nil	160
[UO ₂ (OMPP) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ₂ H ₂ O	31.24 (31.80)	32.18 (32.10)	4.00 (4.31)	11.36 (11.23)	9.00 (9.62)	320
UO ₂ (OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	42.07 (42.64)	16.42 (17.21)	2.70 (2.17)	15.14 (15.05)	6.00 (6.45)	265
UO ₂ (OPP) ₂ H ₂ O	35.38 (35.83)	32.89 (32.54)	2.07 (2.12)	13.24 (12.65)	3.00 (2.71)	310

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Group	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cyclic)	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (oxime)	$\nu_{\text{N-O}}$
OMPP	—	—	1705 (vs, s)	1612 (s, s)	1590 (s, s)	1040 (s, s)
Fe(OMPP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	5.25	—	1625 (s, s)	1600 (s, s)	1565 (m, s)	1155 (s, s)
Mn(OMPP) ₂	5.35	—	1636 (v, vs)	1595 (s, s)	1518 (s, s)	1122 (s, s)
Zn(OMPP) ₂	—	—	1640 (s, s)	1600 (s, s)	1522 (s, s)	1140 (vs, vs)
[VO(OMPP) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ₂ H ₂ O	1.54	—	1615 (s, s)	1595 (s, sh)	1585 (s, s)	1142 (s, s)
[UO ₂ (OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ₂ H ₂ O	—	—	1675-1655 (vs, br)	1588 (s, s)	1560 (s, s)	1148 (s, vs)
OMP	—	—	1700 (vs, m)	1615 (s, s)	1590 (s, s)	1030 (vs, s)
Fe(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	5.02	—	1618 (vs, s)	1612 (s, s)	1565 (s, s)	1070 (vs, vs)
Mn(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	5.42	—	1660 (vs, s)	1620 (s, s)	1580 (s, s)	1060 (vs, vs)
Zn(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	—	—	1625 (vs, s)	1610 (s, sh)	1560 (s, m)	1060 (vs, vs)
[VO(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ₂ H ₂ O	—	—	1670 (vs, s)	1630 (s, br)	1562 (vs, m)	1078 (vs, vs)
UO ₂ (OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	—	—	1665 (s, s)	1520 (m, sh)	1555 (s, s)	1060 (vs, vs)
OPP	—	—	1707 (s, s)	1665 (s, s)	1610 (s, s)	1042 (vs, s)
Fe(OPP) ₂	5.04	—	1610 (s, s)	1625 (s, sh)	1580 (s, br)	1082 (s, s)
Mn(OPP) ₂	5.41	—	1650 (s, s)	1640 (s, sh)	1500 (m, s)	1150 (s, m)
Zn(OPP) ₂ H ₂ O	—	—	1655 (s, s)	1630 (s, br)	1510 (s, s)	1130 (s, br)
VO(OPP) ₂	1.54	—	1642 (s, s)	1590 (w, m)	1510 (s, s)	1105 (vs, vs)
UO ₂ (OPP) ₂ H ₂ O	—	—	1610 (s, s)	1660 (s, sh)	1500 (s, s)	1120 (vs, vs)
ODPP	—	—	1682 (s, s)	1615 (s, s)	1592 (s, s)	1055 (vs, vs)
Fe(ODPP) ₂	4.78	—	1608 (s, s)	1580 (s, sh)	1555 (vs, sh)	1130 (s, br)
Mn(ODPP) ₂	5.53	—	1635 (s, vs)	1592 (m, s)	1495 (s, s)	1095 (s, vs)
Zn(ODPP) ₂	—	—	1633 (s, s)	1600 (s, m)	1490 (s, s)	1102 (s, s)
VO(ODPP) ₂	1.55	—	1615 (s, vs)	1592 (s, s)	1490 (vs, sh)	1160 (s, s)

In the parenthesis first abbreviation indicates intensity and second indicates nature of band, vs=very strong/very sharp, s=strong/sharp, m=medium/medium sharp, w=weak, vb=very broad, br=broad, sh=shoulder.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE Fe(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Electronic transition energy (cm ⁻¹)		B	β	C
	Charge transfer	⁶ T _{2g} → ⁶ E _g			
Fe(OMPP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	23,530	15,900-13,900 ; 9804 (sh)	783	0.74	3132
Fe(OMP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	22,730	11,300 ; 10,200 (sh)	610	0.58	2440
Fe(OPP) ₂	24,390	12,900-11,560 ; 9615 (sh)	643	0.61	2570
Fe(ODPP) ₂	23,260	14,490-12,740 ; 10,310 (sh)	772	0.73	3089

$\nu_{N-O}^{4,9,10}$. The higher ν_{N-O} suggests the presence of intermolecular or intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the ligands¹¹. All metal complexes show higher ν_{N-O} compared to its parent ligand. This may be attributed to bond formation through the nitrogen of the oximino group.

All metal complexes containing water show a broad band in the region 3600-3300 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν_{OH} of water. In ML₂ and ML₂.H₂O type of metal complexes the ν_{C-N} (cyclic) is also lowered indicating that the nitrogen atom of the ring has participated in bonding to metal ions. The broad band around 3100 and 3240 cm⁻¹ in the infrared spectrum of OMP and OPP respectively may be assigned to $\nu_{N-H}^{6,12}$. Infrared spectra of metal complexes of these ligands show similar band in the same region.

The infrared spectra of VO(II) complexes of OMPP and OMP show ν_{V-O} at 958 and 960 cm⁻¹ respectively suggesting mononuclear nature of the complexes^{13,14}. The bands at 875 and 880 cm⁻¹ in the VO(II) complex of OPP and ODPP respectively indicate the presence of associated structure in these complexes¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The infrared spectra of UO₂(II) complexes show two bands ~830 and ~915 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν_{sy} and ν_{asy} of linear O—U—O respectively¹⁹⁻²¹.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the Fe(II) complexes show a broad asymmetric band with same structures and a low energy shoulder. The broad band may be assigned to ⁶T_{2g}→⁶E_g transition in an octahedral field which corresponds to 10 Dq. The low energy shoulder is presumed to be due to a low symmetry ligand field which lifts the two fold degeneracy of the ⁶E_g²². The high energy band might be charge transfer in nature. It is required that 10 Dq should be almost equal to the spin-pairing energy $\pi = 2.5B + 4C \approx 18.5B^{23}$. Thus taking 10 Dq = π , B is calculated. The nephelauxetic ratio β is also derived. The results are given in Table 3. It indicates reduction in B upon coordination. This means that the radial displacement of the d electrons is increased and the effective charge experienced by these electrons is decreased. In other words a decrease in B suggests the partial covalent nature of the M—L bond²⁴.

The spectra of Mn(II) complexes show three bands in normally expected regions for Mn(II) octahedral complex. They may be assigned as follows²⁵ : ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(G) ~16,000 cm⁻¹ ; ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}(G) ~23,000 cm⁻¹ ; ⁶A_{1g}→⁴E_g, ⁴A_{1g}(G) ~25,000 cm⁻¹.

The ⁶A_{1g}→⁴A_{1g}, ⁴E(G) transition energy can be estimated as a ⁶S→⁴G separation energy. The nephelauxetic ratio β, evaluated as a ratio of the term separation energy in the complex to that in the free ion is close to unity, indicates the ionic nature of the M—L bond²⁴.

Examination of the diffuse reflectance spectra of VO(II) complexes leads to : (i) spectrum of each complex shows a very strong band in the region 23000-27000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³B₁→³A₁ transition and (ii) VO(II) complex of OMPP shows a broad visible band centred at 13510 cm⁻¹ with shoulders on either sides. This suggests the low symmetry of the complex²⁶. Pyridine spectra of VO(II) complexes are identical but definitely different from their parent complexes. This indicates the identical stereochemistry of the complex in pyridine. Each pyridine spectrum consists of three bands which may be assigned to the following transitions²⁷ : (i) ²B₂→²E ~13,000 cm⁻¹, (ii) ²B₂→²B₁ ~16,000 cm⁻¹, (iii) ²B₂→²A₁ ~25,000 cm⁻¹.

The low magnetic moments (Table 2) of the Fe(II) complexes may be attributed to the trigonal distortion of the compounds²⁷. This distortion allows the excited ⁶E_g term to be mixed into the ground term by both the crystal field and spin-orbit coupling. The magnetic moments of Mn(II) complexes are lower than that predicted for spin-free d⁵ system with ⁶A_{1g} ground term. The low magnetic moments of these complexes may be due to admixture of Mn(III) complex with Mn(II) complex or may be due to presence of metal-metal interaction. The polymeric nature of the VO(II) complexes may be an important factor for their low moments. [VO(OMP)₂.H₂O].H₂O is diamagnetic.

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